

Sense of community in young people in the district of Moquegua, Peru¹

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to analyze the sense of community in young people in the district of Moquegua, capital city of the Moquegua Region. The possible dependence on some sociodemographic factors (age, gender and level of education) was also analyzed. We worked with a simple random sample of 124 young people from 17 to 30 years old. For the collection of information, the Sanchez Sense of Community Scale (2009) was used. It was found that in 64.5% of the sample a ambivalent sense of community prevails, while in 31.5% the weak level predominates. On the other hand, the sense of community does not depend on the sociodemographic characteristics of the sample.

Keywords: sense of community, neighborhood interaction, interdependence, territorial roots, influence.

Introduction

During the last decades, hand in hand with the passive acceptance of the consolidation of Globalization (Jiménez, 2005), of the so-called crisis of traditional values (Medina, 2015) that runs parallel to it, and of other factors that weaken the importance of social actors (Jiménez, 2005), we recognize the emergence of a sustained process of fragmentation of the community (Wiesenfeld, 2006) and of the deterioration of the assumptions on which it is built. Although the community has understood itself in different ways (Bialakowski, 2010; Causse, 2009; Krause, 2001), so much so that towards the 50s George Hillery identified more than 90 definitions of community, the truth is that since Social Psychology and, more specifically, Community Psychology have focused on it, beyond the territorial meaning that Joseph Gusfield already recognized (cit. in McMillan and Chavis, 1986; Flores, 2005), roughly can be conceived as a space of social relations of support (Montero, 2009). These relationships are established between people who share problems, expectations and interests (Obst, Sandy and Zinkiewicz, 2001), those that are located in different levels: family, neighborhood (Ante y Reyes, 2016; Cueto, 2016; Vallejo-Martín, Moreno-Jiménez y Ríos-Rodríguez, 2017; Yau, 2012), school (Dernowska, 2017; Lenzi et al., 2017; Stornaiuolo, DiZio y Hellmich, 2013), city (Ramos-Vidal, 2014; Seminario, 2014).

This process of fragmentation is fed back by two great forces: a growing individualism (Álvarez, 2009), which is sometimes stimulated by equating with freedom, while the individual can be defined in terms of himself and his own searches (Cienfuegos-Martínez, Saldívar-Garduño, Díaz-Loving and Ávalos-Montoya, 2016), and no longer as part of a community; and a crisis of meaning (Planas-Lladó, Soler-Masó and Feixa-Pampols, 2014) that, while some consider unique in history, others see as a result of a cyclical experience throughout history (Berger and Luckmann, 1996). And precisely because of this, it has ended up attacking the personal experience of being part of a larger group. This feeling, which is identified as a psychological sense of community, in

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Sarason, community feeling (Muñoz, 2014; Sánchez, 2009), or sense of community, in some more recent authors (Ante and Reyes, 2016; Vega and Pereira, 2012 Vidal, Berroeta, Di Masso, Valera and Peró, 2013, Yau, 2012), is understood as a collective feeling experienced by different individuals when they are part of social groups (Ramos-Vidal, 2014).

For a matter of common sense, and following the line of the given argument, it is to be assumed that this process of fragmentation is more noticeable in those societies that go through periods of internal transformation, either by growth or development, as noted by Mishan (1983), or by emigration and depopulation, as has happened in situations of war or internal armed conflict (Morote, 2014). Consequently, the sense of community, which in certain periods of the history of a community can be considered rather homogeneous, ends up weakening and diluting in a dialectical opposition between belonging to the community and privacy (Gómez y Hombrados, 1992), experience most notorious among the youth of a community.

From this perspective, the sense of community transcends its psychological connotation and rescues its original sociological foundation by taking root in the notion of community that derives from it. Thus, it can be understood that belonging to a physical territory is an element that contributes to the identity of the human being (Pérez, 2006). And under that premise, local territoriality gives rise to what Pérez (2006) calls neighborhood community or, in general, community. This implies that in those communities that identify themselves as such around a geographical space, the sense of community would tend to be consistent over time, even when the processes of fragmentation constitute factors of destabilization of the community.

Consequently, this antinomian behavior would be more expected in societies that, although they are growing at the same time, are going through social events linked to their territorial component, which have a relevant impact on the sense of community that their members experience.

It should be noted that, even when the proposals are covered either in the position of Sarason or in that of Mc Millan and Chavis (1986), the definitions of the sense of community tend towards a relatively univocal meaning; situation that is not observed when trying to delimit the operational domain of the construct. In this case, not only the perspectives of approach vary, but the components that are attributed to the construct are different. Thus, while following Sarason, Sánchez (2009) identifies four dimensions: *neighborhood interaction*, *territorial rootedness*, *community integration*, and *influence*, Mc Millan and Chavis (1986) agree on the identification of the *influence* dimension, at the same time that identify three others: *belonging*, *satisfaction of needs* and *shared emotional connection* (Ramos, 2014).

In light of this framework, this study is conceptually located in Sarason's perspective, followed in empirical terms by the sense of community measurement model used by Sánchez (2009). And it is located ontologically in a society that presents the assumptions that define the described antinomy: a growing city, with a marked counterpoint of elements that, as well as modernizing it, also weaken its identity and community experience. It is about the city of Moquegua (Peru), a space where a society of less than 65 thousand people develops, which experiences a sustained advance in terms of economic growth and development, but which went through a set of experiences (an earthquake, the year 2001, overflows and accidents due to the annual flooding of a local river, and a strike of great magnitude, in 2008) that would be understood as coadjuvants

to strengthen the sense of community and serve as palliatives to the process of fragmentation of the community.

Considering that these facts are of daily reading among the adult population of the city, we have tried to approach the sense of community in a group of young people from the city of Moquegua, to the extent that many of them were not immediate actors of the events described, but only receivers of information that has remained in the collective imagination of the society in which they live.

In this line, this study aimed to analyze the sense of community in young people of the city of Moquegua (Peru), and determine their dependence on some sociodemographic factors, such as age, sex and educational level, that different studies (Marín, Pons, Grande and Gil, 2002, Muñoz, 2014, Sánchez, 2009, Vallejo-Martín, Moreno-Jiménez and Ríos Rodríguez, 2017) have identified as significant.

Research methods

Sampling and sample characteristics

We worked with a simple random sample of 124 young people from 17 to 30 years of the district of Moquegua, between men and women. This district is located in the Mariscal Nieto province, Moquegua region, in southern Peru. The sample was determined for a confidence level of 95%, $p = 0.80$, $q = 0.20$ and an error of 0.07.

Regarding the characteristics of the sample, a proportion of 30.6% was found in the intervals from 17 to 19 years and from 20 to 22 years; of 20.2% in the range of 23 to 25 years; and 18.6% in the range of 26 to 30 years. The average age was 21.7 years, with a deviation of 3.42 years, a median of 21 years, a coefficient of variation of 15.6%, and a greater concentration towards the lower age ranges.

With regard to gender, the group was mostly made up of women: 83 girls (67% of the total) compared to 41 boys (33%). On the other hand, the vast majority of young people (93.5%) have higher education, while only 4.8% of the group has not passed secondary school. There were no cases of young people with primary education or without education.

Variables and measures

To measure the *sense of community*, the *Sense of Community Scale* was applied (Sánchez, 2009), questionnaire with Likert scale of 18 items, which is based on the Sarason theory, and explores four dimensions: *positive neighborhood interaction*, of 5 items; *interdependence*, of 5 items; *territorial rootess*, of 6 items; and *influence*, of 2 items. The answers are scored using a Likert-type scale whose values vary from 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally agree). Three categories of interpretation of the sense of community were proposed: weak (18 to 42 points), ambivalent (43 to 66 points), and strong (67 to 90 points). In the case of dimensions, the categories are the same, but the scores that define them are different: *positive neighborhood interaction* and *interdependence* (weak, 5 to 11 points, ambivalent, 12 to 18, and strong, 19 to 25); *territorial rootess* (weak, 6 to 14 points, ambivalent, 15 to 22, and strong, 23 to 30); and *influence* (weak, 2 to 4 points, ambivalent, 5 to 7, and strong, 8 to 10).

The instrument has evidence of validity based on the construct (Sánchez, 2009), analyzed by factorial analysis of main components with oblimin rotation; and excellent internal consistency, with coefficients alpha - Cronbach of 0.90 and 0.85, measured in two Spanish communities. In correspondence with these data, in the first study conducted

here (Moquegua, Peru), a good total internal consistency was found, with an alpha Cronbach coefficient of 0.881.

Analysis of data

An analysis of the variable was done in an integral way and according to its dimensions by frequency tables; and their possible dependence on age, gender and educational level was analyzed through Fisher's exact test.

RESULTS

When analyzing the sense of community, it was found that the majority of young people is distributed in the ambivalent category (64.5%), followed by the strong category (31.5%). In contrast, only 4% of the set, do not exceed the weak level.

Figure 1. Level of sense of community

With regard to *positive neighborhood interaction*, the majority of young people are in the ambivalent category (57.3%), while there is a close distribution in the weak (19.4%) and strong (23.4%) categories. In summary, more than 75% of the young people who were part of the sample do not establish a positive neighborhood interaction that allows them to experience a strong sense of community.

With regard to *interdependence*, the majority of young people are at the strong level (70.2%). On the other hand, 24.2% is distributed in the ambivalent category; while only 5.6% is distributed at the weak level.

With regard to *territorial rootness*, the majority of young people are in the ambivalent category (66.1%). On the other hand, 13.7% is distributed in the weak category, which means that they are not adequately integrated with their neighborhood. In contrast, 20.2% is distributed at the strong level. In short, almost 80% of young people who participated in the study have not achieved an adequate sense of belonging to the territory in which they live.

And as far as *influence* is concerned, the majority of young people are also in the ambivalent category (56.5%). On the other hand, 12.9% are distributed in the weak category. In contrast, 30.6% of the set is distributed at the strong level. In summary, almost 70% of young people who participated in the study recognize that they have little or no influence on their community.

Figure 2. Level of sense of community by dimensions

On the other hand, an index is plotted that relates the accumulated score to the maximum possible score in each dimension (Fig. 1). In this case, following the trend observed in the frequency tables, the highest value falls on the *interdependence* dimension, with an index of 0.782, which means that the accumulated score in this dimension reached 78.2% of the possible total. In the case of the other dimensions, the indices were lower: 0.617, for *positive neighborhood interaction*; 0.642, for *territorial rootness*; and also 0.662, for *influence*.

Figure 3. Sense of Community Index

Regarding the possible dependence of sense of community on the sociodemographic factors considered, no relationship was found between sense of community and age, gender or educational level. When analyzing the relationship between sociodemographic factors and the dimensions of sense of community, it was found that age does not relate to any of the dimensions of the variable. However, a relationship was found between gender and influence ($\chi^2 = 6.080$, $p = 0.047$), but not with respect to the other dimensions of community feeling. Likewise, a relationship was found between the level of instruction and the positive neighborhood interaction for a level of 0.1 ($\chi^2 = 5.088$, $p = 0.056$), but not for a level of 0.05. And no relationship was found between the level of instruction and the other dimensions of community feeling.

DISCUSSION

Towards an overview of the findings

When analyzing the sense of community, it was found that the majority of young people is distributed in the ambivalent category (64.5%), followed by the strong category, although with a very distant proportion (31.5%). This means that young people assume an important sense of community, and not a rather elusive attitude, as happens in other scenarios (Muñoz, 2014; Vallejo-Martín et al., 2017). This trend is also observed at the level of variable dimensions, where the ambivalent category obtains proportions greater than 50% (57.3% for *positive neighborhood interaction*, 66.1% for *territorial rootness* and 56.5% for *influence*, with the exception of *interdependence*, which highlights the strong category with more than 70% of cases. In this way, the results are part of a framework of findings that show average levels of community feeling (Sánchez, 2009; Vallejo-Martín et al., 2017), although in this case the tendency towards higher levels is evident.

Implications at the community level

On the other hand, it is clear that the sense of community appears as a variable that does not depend on sociodemographic characteristics. The results distance themselves from the findings of Sánchez (2009) and Muñoz (2014), based on age; from Vallejo-Martín et al. (2017), regarding the level of instruction, as a component of the socioeconomic level; and from Marín et al. (2002) about sex and other variables. The only case of a significant relationship occurs between the gender and the *influence* dimension, where there is a difference between the group of women (63.8%) and the group of men (only 41.46%) in the category of ambivalent influence. Could it be suspected that girls are less sure of their influence in their community?

In fact, the data are insufficient to establish a conclusion in this regard. In addition, this city stands out for an important tradition of female participation in different areas of social demand, ranging from an early feminist reevaluation at the end of the 19th century (Atencia-Oliden, 2015), until the election of one of the first regional presidents in Peru in the nascent 21st century (ONPE, 2003).

In that sense, there is solid evidence regarding the social postponement of women in relation to men in Peruvian society in general, in a way that goes beyond the current situation and can only be described as structural (Acuña y Blanco, 2009; Cueva et al., 2016; INEI, 2015), and of some degree of social postponement in the region. Moquegua, in particular (Lizarzaburu, Campos, Franco y Campos, 2017).

But it is possible that the figures at the level of region, city and district are different from those corresponding to the national level, as found by Mamani (2014) for the nearby city of Ilo, located on the coasts of the same department. It is precisely these differences with respect to the figures at the country level that allow us to suggest that education is a possible homogenization factor for society in Moquegua (Sugimaru y León, 2015), to the point that gender-related differences seem to bow to the weight of the sense of community.

Implications for research

Finally, as a corollary, the following is stated: First, this study is part of a framework of interpretation of the sense of community (Meza, 2009; Montero, 2009), to a certain extent postponed, in comparison with the validation studies of the construct (Ante and Reyes, 2016, Muñoz, 2014, Sánchez, 2009). And second, although the results indicate a

tendency toward medium and high values of sense of community, it would be convenient to extend the analysis of the variable to other samples, both of young people and of older adults, in order to evaluate whether it is a conjunctural finding or, if rather, obeys structural reasons that speak of a situation different from those identified in other spaces.

CONCLUSIONS

Regarding the sense of community, the majority of young people is distributed in the ambivalent category (64.5%), followed by the strong category (31.5%). At the level of dimensions, the ambivalent category predominates in positive neighborhood interaction (57.3%), territorial roots (66.1%) and influence (56.5%), while the strong level predominates in interdependence (70.2%).

On the other hand, it was found that the sense of community does not depend on the age, sex or educational level of the young people; in all cases, Fisher's exact test was not significant ($p > 0.05$).

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